
Satisfaction on Nursing Care among Admitted Patients in Secondary Level Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nurses are the vital for any health care setting and basic nursing cares is concerned with helping a patient and meet his or her basic needs. The main role of nursing today is to help the individual to attain or maintain the optimal level of health. In Bangladesh, health care service is mostly curative oriented and hospital based; where the quality of service is a major concern particularly care provided by nurses. Therefore, in the present study the researcher interested to measure the degree of patients' satisfaction and its relationship with quality of nursing care, which is measured by three important aspects of nurses including nurse's attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Many previous researchers have studied patient satisfaction towards nursing services in healthcare setting using NCPSS with Likert scale. But in this study the researcher used Risser's patient's satisfaction scale.

Materials and Methods: This cross sectional study was conducted from January to December 2015, purposively about 329 admitted patients of male, female and gyene & obstetrical ward at Adhunik Sadar Hospital, Nilphamary to find out the level of satisfaction on nursing care among admitted patients in secondary level Hospital. Data were collected by the researcher himself by face to face interview with a pretested semi-structured questionnaire.

Results: Result reveals that regarding attitude 52.6% were satisfied, 33.4% and 14.0% were highly satisfied and dissatisfied respectively. Regarding nurses' behavior 53.8% were satisfied, 32.5% and 13.7% were highly satisfied and dissatisfied respectively. Regarding nurses' interpersonal relationship 44.4% were highly satisfied, 40.4% and 15.2% were satisfied and dissatisfied respectively.

Conclusion: Nurses need to improve their attitude, behavior, and interpersonal relationship for patients' satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Patient satisfaction, Attitude, Behavior, Interpersonal-relationship, Acceptance, Responsible.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Health care is one of the basic needs to human being and it is a public right. Health care refers to services provided to the individual or community by the agent of the health services or professions different types of health institutions are available in our country both in public and private sectors for the delivery of the health care services to the people. Health care up to the patient's satisfaction is very much desired. Dissatisfaction of the patient's regarding health care in our country is frequently heard of [1].

In recent years, the focus on consumer is in a highly competitive environment has led to increased interest in measuring patient satisfaction with health care. Patient satisfaction is often considered as an important parameter of the quality of care [2].

Measurement of patients' satisfaction on health care may be difficult because one patient is satisfied to something but another may not be satisfied to same thing, satisfaction is vary widely from patient to patient. Satisfaction is the

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psychological state that results from confirmation or disconfirmation of expectations with reality [3].

Patient satisfaction is frequently defined as the extent to which patients' expectations of care matched the actual care received. Based on a thorough concept analysis of patient satisfaction, Patient satisfaction with nursing care as "The patients' subjective evaluation of the cognitive emotional response that results from the interaction of the patients' expectation of nursing care and their perceptions of actual nurse behaviors". Patient satisfaction as "the degree to which nursing care needs patients' expectations in terms of art of care, technical quality, physical environment, availability and continuity of care, and the efficacy of care"[4].

Some researcher have identified adherence to medically prescribed regimens as an outcome of patients satisfaction with nursing care. A dissatisfied patient is not considered psychologically or socially well and thus, the goal of nursing has not been attained. It is important for nurses to let patients express their views of care and incorporate these views in to the provided care. As the patient centered nursing care is essentially plays an important role to increase patients' satisfaction considered as indicator for the quality of services [5].

The highly educated nurses in Bangladesh are not interested in bedside nursing after getting qualified; they are more inclined to work in administrative and academic sectors. Therefore, they cannot provide the qualitative care that the patients deserve and thus the patient satisfaction level is low. There is no M. Sc. nursing college in our country, As a result, there is a lack of personnel to train the student nurses about quality health care and patient satisfaction [6].

The satisfaction of patients with nursing care is crucial in order to identify the area of dissatisfaction and at the same time improve the nursing services. It is known to all that nursing services are not well organized in Bangladesh. As patient satisfaction with nursing care was not assessed adequately or not at all gain attention in our country, this study would be the baseline on this direction and helpful for improving the nursing services in Bangladesh. Finally, it will expect that this study finding generate information profile on expectation and perception toward the indoor patient service provided. This might give a better understanding from meaning of satisfaction from the client perspective and it would have a significant implication to the hospital management [7].

Therefore, in the present study the researcher interested to measure the degree of patients' satisfaction and its relationship with quality of nursing care, which is measured by three important aspects of nurses including nurse's attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Many previous researchers have studied patient satisfaction towards nursing services in healthcare setting using NCPSS with Likert scale. But in this study the researcher used Risser's patient's satisfaction scale.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

This cross sectional study was conducted from January to December 2015, purposively about 329 admitted patients of male, female and gyene & obstetrical ward at Adhunik Sadar Hospital, Nilphamary to find out the level of satisfaction on nursing care among admitted patients in secondary level Hospital.

Study design: Cross sectional descriptive study.

Study place: The study was conducted at Adhunik Sadar Hospital, Nilphamary. Study population was selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria.

For this study, the researcher conveniently selected following wards -Male general wards, Female general wards and Gyenae and obstetrical ward.

Study period: The study was conducted from January to December, 2015.

Sample size: Sample size was 329 patients.

Sampling technique: Purposive sampling technique was use.

Subjects & selection method: The study population were admitted patients of male, female and gyene and obstetrical ward at Adhunik Sadar Hospital, Nilphamary.

Inclusion criteria included

1. Only hospital admitted patients.(3 days and more)
2. Age of the respondent were 18 years and above.
3. Patients those were able to communicate and well oriented.
4. Agree to participate in the study. **Exclusion criteria**

1. Mentally disable patients
2. Unconscious patients or seriously ill patients
3. Those who will not interested

Procedure methodology: After written informed consent was obtained, a well design semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data by the researcher himself by face to face interview.

The study was conducted at Adhunik Sadar Hospital, Nilphamary. Study population was selected according to inclusion and exclusion criteria.

For this study, the researcher conveniently selected following

- wards - □ Male general wards:
- Female general wards
 - Gyenae and obstetrical ward

Statistical analysis

The data collected from the respondents were analyzed. After completion of data collection, to maintain consistency, the data were checked and edited manually and verified before tabulation. Data were coded, entered and analyzed in a computer. Data analysis was done by using SPSS (statistical package for social science) version 20 statistical software. The findings of the study were presented by frequency, percentage in tables and graphs. Means and standard deviation for continuous variables and frequency distribution for categorical variable were used to describe the characteristics of the total sample. Relationships of the

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categorical data were assessed using Chi-square test to explore the association.

III. RESULT

Table 1: This table shows the highest number 121(36.8%) of the respondents belonged to age group 26-35 years and lowest number 8(2.4%) of the respondents belonged to age 56-65years. The mean age was 35.71, and the standard deviation was ± 9.759 . Among 329 respondents, male were 171(52%) whereas 158(48%) of the respondents were female and from them highest 113 (43.30%) were never went to school, 107 (32.7%) were primary passed, 63 (19.10%) were Junior school passed and lowest 46 (14.00%) were SSC passed and above. Here, the highest group of the respondents' occupation

142(43.20%) were housewife and the lowest 02(.60%) were student. Rest of them 21(6.40%) were services holder, 68(20.70%) were farmer, 49(14.90%) were doing business and 47(14.30%) were day labors. The highest portion of the respondent 151(45.9%) had monthly family income from 10000 - 19999 taka and the lowest portion of the respondents 25(7.6%) had monthly family income from 30,000- 39,999 taka. 127(38.6%) and 26(7.9%) respondents had monthly income from 20000- 29999 taka and 40000 - 49999 taka respectively. The mean monthly income was Tk. 20000/= with the SD ± 8375.47 . Majorities of the respondents lived in rural area that were 226(68.70%) and 86(26.10%) and 17(5.20%) were living in urban and slum area respectively.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents by demographic characteristics (n = 329)

Age group of the respondents	Frequency	Percent
16-25 years	70	21.3
26-35 years	121	36.8
36-45 years	96	29.2
46-55 years	34	10.3
56-65 years	8	2.4
Mean = 35.71years, S.D = ± 9.759		
Sex of the respondents		
Female	158	48
Male	171	52
Educational status of the respondents		
Never went to school	113	43.30
Primary passed	107	32.7
Junior school passed	63	19.10
SSC passed and above	46	14.00
Occupational status of the respondents		
Housewife	142	43.20
Student	02	.60
Services holder	21	6.40
Farmer	68	20.70
Business	49	14.90
Day labors	47	14.30
Monthly Income of the respondents		
10000 -19999 Taka	151	45.9
20000 - 29999 Taka	127	38.6
30000 - 39999 Taka	25	7.6
Mean = 20000 Tk, SD ± 8375.47		
Residential of the respondents		
Rural	226	68.70
Urban	86	26.10
Slum	17	5.20

Figure 1 shows the admission ward of the respondents. Among 329 respondents 171(52%) were in male ward, 98(30%) were in female ward and rest of the 60(18%) respondents were in gyenae and obstetrical ward.

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Figure 1: Distribution of the respondents by admission ward (n = 329)

Figure 2 shows that the admission history in hospital in last year of the respondents. Among 329 respondents 257(78.10%) were admitted in hospital first time and 72(21.90%) had history of previous admission.

Figure 2: Distribution of the respondents by admission history in hospital in last year (n = 329)

Figure 3 shows that opinion of the respondents about nursing care that they provide immediately after admission. Majority of the respondents 191(58.0%) were agreed, 90(27.4%) were strongly agreed and 48(14.6%) were disagreed of the opinion.

Figure 3: Opinion of the respondents about nursing care that they provide immediately after admission (n = 329)

Table 2: This table shows nurses' Attitude related Opinion. Among 329 respondents 145(44.1%) were uncertain with on nurse informs about the services available in the hospital, 125(38.0%) were agreed, 34(10.3%) were disagreed and 25(7.6%) were strongly agreed of the opinion. Among 329 respondents 121(36.8%) were strongly disagreed with nurse explains about the result of the test even s/he is busy, 113(34.3%) were disagreed, 70(24.0%) were uncertain and 25(7.6%) were agreed of the opinion. Majority of the respondents 212(64.4%) were agreed with nurses does not feel disturb during explain illness and type of treatment, 49(14.9%) were disagreed, 43(13.1%) were uncertain and

25(7.6%) were strongly agreed of the opinion. Most of the respondents 205(62.3%) were agreed with nurses listen and talk with respect, 62(18.8%) were strongly Agreed, 33(10.0%) were uncertain and 29(8.8%) were disagreed of the opinion. Among 329 respondents 158(48.0%) were agreed with nurses always provide care with responsibility, 73(22.2%) were strongly agreed and uncertain and 25(7.6%) were disagreed of the opinion. Majority of the respondents 233(70.8%) were agreed with nurses shows helping attitude with relatives, 38(11.6%) were strongly agreed, 32(9.7%) were uncertain and 26(7.9%) were disagreed of the opinion.

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Table 2: Distribution of the respondents by nurses' Attitude related Opinion (n = 329)

Nurse informs availability of the service	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	25	7.6
Agree	125	38.0
Uncertain	145	44.1
Disagree	34	10.3
Nurse explains about the result of the test even s/he is busy		
Agree	25	7.6
Uncertain	70	24.0
Disagree	113	34.3
Strongly Disagree	121	36.8
Nurses does not feel disturb during explain illness and type of treatment		
Strongly Agree	25	7.6
Agree	212	64.4
Uncertain	43	13.1
Disagree	49	14.9
Nurses listen and talk with respect		
Strongly Agree	62	18.8
Agree	205	62.3
Uncertain	33	10.0
Disagree	29	8.8
Nurses always provide care with responsibility		
Strongly Agree	73	22.2
Agree	158	48.0
Uncertain	73	22.2
Disagree	25	7.6
Nurses shows helping attitude with relatives		
Strongly Agree	38	11.6
Agree	233	70.8
Uncertain	32	9.7
Disagree	26	7.9
Total	329	100.0

Figure 4: This figure shows the opinion of the respondents on nurses is very much concern about patients' needs. Among 329 respondents 167(50.8%) were agreed, 48(14.6%) were strongly agreed, 45(13.7%), 42(12.8%) and 27(8.2%) were disagree, uncertain and strongly disagreed respectively of the opinion.

Figure 4: Opinion of the respondents on nurses is very much concern about patients' needs (n = 329)

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Table 3: This table shows of the respondents on nurses' behavior related Opinion. Majority of the respondents 186(56.5%) were agreed with nurses' competently provide care, 61(18.5%) were strongly agreed, 47(14.3%) were uncertain and 35(10.6%) were disagreed of the opinion. Most of the respondents 266(80.9%) were agreed with nurses accurately explain how to use medical instruction, 24(7.3%) were uncertain, 21(6.4%) were disagreed and 18(5.5%) were strongly agreed of the opinion. Among 329 respondents

145(44.10%) were uncertain with nurses finish their work timely to maintain quality of care, 142(43.20%) were agreed, 42(12.80%) were disagreed of the opinion. From 329 respondents 133(40.4%) were uncertain, 11 with nurses are good mood even they are busy, 133(40.4%) were uncertain, 85(25.8%) were disagreed of the opinion. Majority of the respondents 179(54.40%) were agreed with nurses gives good advice, 76(23.1%) were strongly agreed, 44(13.4%) were disagreed and 30(9.1%) were uncertain of the opinion.

Table 3: Distribution of the respondents by nurses' behavior related Opinion (n = 329)

Nurses competently provide care	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	61	18.5
Agree	186	56.5
Uncertain	47	14.3
Disagree	35	10.6
Nurses accurately explain how to use medical instruction		
Strongly Agree	18	5.5
Agree	266	80.9
Uncertain	24	7.3
Disagree	21	6.4
Nurses finish their work timely to maintain quality of care		
Strongly Agree	00	00
Agree	142	43.20
Uncertain	145	44.10
Disagree	42	12.70
Nurses are good mood even they are busy		
Agree	111	33.7
Uncertain	133	40.4
Disagree	85	25.8
Nurses gives good advice		
Strongly Agree	76	23.1
Agree	179	54.4
Uncertain	30	9.1
Disagree	44	13.4
Total	329	100.0

Table 4: This table shows nurses' interpersonal relationship related Opinion. Majority of the respondents 171(52.0%) were agreed with nurses understand in listening to a patient's problems, 128(38.9%) were strongly agreed and 30(9.1%) were uncertain of the opinion. Among 329 respondents 162(49.2%) were agreed with can ask questions to nurse freely, 133(40.4%) were strongly agree and 36(10.3%) were disagree of the opinion. From 329 respondents 168(51.1%) were agreed with nurses talk with you about your problems even they are busy, 88(26.7%) were disagree 38(11.6%) were uncertain and 35(10.6%) were strongly disagree of the

opinion. Majority of the respondents 234(71.1%) were agreed with nurses behave friendly during providing care, 41(12.5%) were disagreed and 27(8.2%) were strongly agreed and uncertain of the opinion. Among 329 respondents 189(57.4%) were agreed with talking to the nurse feel comfortable, 118(35.9%) were strongly agreed and 22(6.7%) were disagreed of the opinion. Among 329 respondents 156(47.4%) were uncertain with nurses maintain confidentiality of the patients, 134(40.7%) were agreed and 39(11.9%) were strongly agreed of the opinion.

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Table 4: Distribution of the respondents by nurses' interpersonal relationship related Opinion (n = 329)

Nurses understand in listening to a patient's problems	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	128	38.9
Agree	171	52.0
Uncertain	30	9.1
You can ask questions to nurse freely		
Strongly Agree	133	40.4
Agree	162	49.2
Disagree	34	10.3
Nurses talk with you about your problems even they are busy		
Agree	168	51.1
Uncertain	38	11.6
Disagree	88	26.7
Strongly Disagree	35	10.6
Nurses behave friendly during providing care		
Strongly Agree	27	8.2
Agree	234	71.1
Uncertain	27	8.2
Disagree	41	12.5
Talking to the nurse feel comfortable		
Strongly Agree	118	35.9
Agree	189	57.4
Disagree	22	6.7
Nurses maintain confidentiality of the patients		
Uncertain	156	47.4
Agree	134	40.7
Strongly Agree	39	11.9
Total	329	100.0

Figure 5: This figure shows the percentage distribution of the level of satisfaction of the patients regarding nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Result reveals that regarding attitude 52.6% were satisfied, 33.4% and 14.0% were highly satisfied and dissatisfied respectively. Regarding

nurses' behavior 53.8% were satisfied, 32.5% and 13.7% were highly satisfied and dissatisfied respectively. Regarding nurses' interpersonal relationship 44.4% were highly satisfied, 40.4% and 15.2% were satisfied and dissatisfied respectively.

Figure 5: Level of satisfaction of the patients regarding nurses' attitude, Behavior and Interpersonal Relationship (n = 329)

Table 6 shows the distribution of perceived level of satisfaction of patients towards nurses' attitude, behavior and

interpersonal relationship within their educational status group. In these regard, majority of the patients irrespective of

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educational status were either highly satisfied or satisfied towards nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Chi-square test was done to see the association between respondents' educational status and nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Test revealed that the

observed differences in between groups were statistically significant where for nurses' attitude ($\chi^2 = 16.115$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.05$) nurses' behavior ($\chi^2 = 27.920$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$) and nurses' interpersonal relationship ($\chi^2 = 48.590$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 6: Relationship between educational status and patients' satisfaction regarding nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship (n = 329)

Educational Qualification	Attitude			Behavior			Interpersonal Relationship		
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied
Never went to School	35 31.0%	51 45.1%	27 23.9%	35 31.0%	51 45.1%	27 23.9%	53 46.9%	33 29.2%	27 23.9%
Primary	40 37.4%	57 53.3%	10 9.3%	44 41.1%	51 47.7%	12 11.2%	61 57.0%	29 27.1%	17 15.9%
Junior School	19 30.2%	40 63.5%	4 6.3%	20 31.7%	40 63.5%	3 4.8%	22 34.9%	39 61.9%	2 3.2%
SSC and Above	16 34.8%	25 54.3%	5 10.9%	8 17.4%	35 76.1%	3 6.5%	10 21.7%	32 69.6%	4 8.7%
Total	110 33.4%	173 52.6%	46 14.0%	107 32.5%	177 53.8%	45 13.7%	146 44.4%	133 40.4%	50 15.2%
	$\chi^2 = 16.115$ $df = 6$ $p = 0.013$			$\chi^2 = 27.920$ $df = 6$ $p = 0.000$			$\chi^2 = 48.590$ $df = 6$ $p = 0.000$		

Table 7 shows the distribution of perceived level of satisfaction of patients towards nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship within their occupation. In these regard, majority of the patients irrespective of occupation were either highly satisfied or satisfied towards nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Chi-square test was done to see the association between respondents' educational status and nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Test revealed that the observed differences in between groups were statistically significant where for $p < 0.001$.

Table 7: Relationship between occupation and patients' satisfaction regarding nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship (n = 329)

Occupation	Attitude			Behavior			Interpersonal Relationship		
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied
Service	05 23.8%	15 71.4%	01 4.8%	06 28.6%	15 71.4%	00 0.0%	08 38.1%	11 52.4%	02 9.5%
Farmer	24 35.3%	36 52.9%	08 11.8%	07 10.3%	47 69.1%	14 20.6%	16 23.5%	37 54.4%	15 22.1%
House Wife	40 28.2%	92 64.8%	10 7.0%	62 43.7%	70 49.3%	10 7.0%	78 54.9%	50 35.2%	14 9.9%
Student	01 50.0%	01 50.0%	00 0.0%	02 100.0%	00 0.0%	00 0.0%	01 50.0%	01 50.0%	00 0.0%
Business	20 40.8%	12 24.5%	17 34.7%	14 28.6%	21 42.9%	14 28.6%	20 40.8%	18 36.7%	11 22.4%
Day Labour	20 42.6%	17 36.2%	10 21.3%	16 34.0%	24 51.1%	07 14.9%	23 48.9%	16 34.0%	08 17.0%
Total	110 33.4%	173 52.6%	46 14.0%	107 32.5%	177 53.8%	45 13.7%	146 44.4%	133 40.4%	50 15.2%
	$\chi^2 = 42.679$ $df = 10$ $p = 0.000$			$\chi^2 = 43.953$ $df = 10$ $p = 0.000$			$\chi^2 = 23.773$ $df = 10$ $p = 0.000$		

IV. DISCUSSION

In this study shows the opinion of the respondents on nurses provide care immediately after admission. Majority 58.0% respondents were agreed, 27.4% were strongly agreed and 14.6% were disagreed of the opinion and the opinion of the respondents on nurse informs about the services available in the hospital. 44.1% were uncertain, 38.0% were agreed, 10.3% were disagreed and 7.6% were strongly agreed of the opinion. Another study showed that 43.55% and 22.735% respondents agree and strongly agree respectively that nurses provide care immediately after admission and 41.53% respondents agreed that nurse inform about the services available in the hospital [8].

In the current study, level of satisfaction of the patients regarding nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship was assessed. The result revealed that regarding nurses' attitude high proportions of respondents (52.60%) were satisfied and lowest proportion (14.00%) were dissatisfied. Similarly regarding behavior (53.80%) respondents were satisfied and (13.70%) respondents were dissatisfied. On the other hand, regarding interpersonal relationship, 44.40%, 40.40% were highly satisfied and satisfied respectively and 15.20% respondents were dissatisfied. No similar study was found in the country. However, two studies were conducted about nurses' self-evaluation on their knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP) at two setting: Rajshahi Medical College Hospital- to examine nurses KAP regarding pressure ulcer prevention and Khulna Medical College hospital- for examining KAP of postoperative pain management. Both studies found nurses low level of knowledge and attitude and practice

This study shows the distribution of perceived level of satisfaction of patients towards nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship within their educational status group. Patients satisfaction concerning nurse's attitude and behavior, it is viewed that the highest percentage of patients were satisfied (never went to school=45.1%, 45.1% primary =53.3%, 47.7% junior school=63.5%, 63.5% and SSC and above =54.3%, 76.1% respectively). Level of satisfaction towards nurses' interpersonal relationship found that proportion of never went to school and primary respondents were higher 46.9% and 57.0% respectively in highly satisfied and junior school and SSC and above were higher in satisfied that are 61.9% and 69.6% respectively. Chi-square test was done to see the association between respondents' educational status and nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Test revealed that the observed differences in between groups were statistically significant where for nurses' attitude ($\chi^2 = 16.115$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.05$) nurses' behavior ($\chi^2 = 27.920$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$) and nurses' interpersonal relationship ($\chi^2 = 48.590$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$). No available study was found in this aspect to compare with this study.

In this study shows the distribution of the patient's occupations against their perceived level of satisfaction towards nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal

relationship. Findings illustrated that the respondents' occupation including service, farmer, housewife, and students, had the highest number those expressing satisfied towards nurses' attitude as 71.4%, 52.9%, 64.8%, and 50%, respectively and highly satisfied business man 40.8% and day labour 42.6%. Patients' with satisfied towards behavior, service was 71.4%, farmer 69.1%, housewife 49.3%, business 42.9% and day labour 51.1%. Whereas, patients with highly satisfied for interpersonal relationship, housewife 54.9%, business 40.8% and day labour 48.9% on the other hand service holder 52.4% and farmer 54.4% were satisfied. Chi-square test was done to see the association between respondents' occupation and nurses' attitude, behavior and interpersonal relationship. Test revealed that the observed differences in between groups were statistically significant where for $p < 0.001$. No available study was found in this aspect to compare with this study.

This study result revealed that the overall level of satisfaction on nursing care of the respondents 48% were satisfied 42% were highly satisfied and 10% were dissatisfied. The mean of patient satisfaction was 66.0486 (out of 140 scores). Similar study found that highly satisfied with skill and competence of the nurses 80%, co-ordination between nurse and hospital staff 80% of the respondents [9]. Another study satisfaction with nursing care it was found that most of the patients were satisfied as 52% expressed excellent satisfaction, 44% very good and only 4% reported good satisfaction [10] Not consistent because, socio economic discrepancy differ in country.

V. CONCLUSION

On the basis of discussion the conclusion may derived from the result of this study is that satisfaction of hospitalized patients has direct relationship with nursing service. Although the average patients' satisfaction is satisfactory level, percentage of patients with satisfied 48% is not close to the highly satisfied level 42%. These study findings would help to improve the quality of nursing care in order to increase patients' satisfaction. Thus, the study suggests that nurses need to improve their attitude, behavior, and interpersonal relationship for patients' satisfaction.

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